

On the interrelation of 1/f neural noise and norepinephrine system activity during motor response inhibition

Supplemental material

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Figure S1: Neural noise parameter for each channel and subject

The neural noise parameter is given for each subject and channel. Channels are depicted in rows, subjects in columns. Colors indicate the neural noise parameter values.

Figure S2: Neural noise parameter with outlier correction applied
 Outliers were defined as exceeding 3 SD from the mean slope and replaced by the median slope.

Figure S3: Neural noise parameter excluding vs. including alpha band

Table S1: Correlation of theta band power and neural noise parameter

Results of the correlation analysis of the mean theta band power for the time window 0-1000 ms after stimulus onset and neural noise parameter for the same time window for each channel. P-value and r-value are given.

Channel	p	r	Channel	p	r
AF3	0,010	0,374	FT10	0,000	0,610
AF4	0,013	0,361	FT7	0,001	0,481
AF7	0,627	0,073	FT8	0,004	0,409
AF8	0,002	0,447	FT9	0,172	0,203
AFZ	0,001	0,470	FZ	0,001	0,480
C3	0,002	0,431	IZ	0,027	0,323
C4	0,156	0,210	O1	0,367	0,135
C5	0,139	0,219	O10	0,430	0,118
C6	0,352	0,139	O2	0,637	0,071
CP1	0,160	0,208	O9	0,769	0,044
CP2	0,066	0,270	OZ	0,376	0,132
CP3	0,001	0,469	P1	0,003	0,422
CP4	0,004	0,416	P10	0,528	0,094
CP5	0,206	0,188	P11	0,108	0,238
CP6	0,104	0,240	P12	0,006	0,393
CPZ	0,033	0,311	P2	0,013	0,359
CZ	0,171	0,203	P3	0,292	0,157
F1	0,027	0,323	P4	0,481	0,105
F2	0,006	0,397	P7	0,943	0,011
F5	0,019	0,341	P8	0,580	-0,083
F6	0,161	0,208	P9	0,738	0,050
FC1	0,095	0,246	PO1	0,409	0,123
FC2	0,156	0,210	PO2	0,745	0,049
FC3	0,028	0,321	PZ	0,084	0,255
FC4	0,300	0,154	T7	0,372	0,133
FC5	0,121	0,229	T8	0,035	0,309
FC6	0,002	0,444	TP10	0,162	0,207
FCZ	0,017	0,347	TP7	0,125	0,227
FP1	0,008	0,381	TP8	0,137	0,220
FP2	0,017	0,348	TP9	0,088	0,251

Mean correlation 0.258 (SD = 0.14)